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Inculcating the Value of Integrity in Young Persons in Ibadan Local Government Areas, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Integrity, the quality of being honest, upright and of good character has always been an essential ingredient for societal and national development. The observed lack of integrity among young persons in Ibadan Local Government Areas, (consisting of Ona Ara, Lagelu, Egbeda, Akinyele, Oluyole, Iddo), and at an increasing rate, is worrisome. This observed loss of integrity in individuals, families, communities, and Nigeria at large has been entrenched deep as a cultural worldview, militating against the general progress of the younger generation. To restore the value of integrity therefore, change must also occur at the deep level of their cultural perceptions, as efforts to change patterns of behaviour will at best be temporary. This paper suggests that intense efforts be made, by governmental and non-governmental agencies, to re-orientate both the elderly who naturally should teach values and beliefs, and the upcoming generation whose decay needs to be salvaged, as a strategy for holistic transformation of society. The curriculum to be utilized has already been put together by Nigeria's National Orientation Programme. Lack of integrity by those who should teach by precept and lifestyle has not permitted the programme to bring desired change in young Nigerians. Leaders, elders and parents who do what they say they will do, and who passionately pursue intentional re-orientation at the core of culture, are the solution to restoring integrity in the young in Ibadan Local Government Areas and Nigeria at large. To achieve this feat, not only should all hands be on deck, funding it must be prioritized by all.

1. Introduction

The nation, Nigeria as it stands currently is fraught with multiple anomalies in the socio-economic, political, educational and other spheres of life. The corruption ranking of Nigeria is 150 out of 180 countries, and she has 24 points out of 100 on the Corruption Perceptions index, reported by Transparency International for 2023 (Trading Economics, 2023) Middle aged Nigerians have tales of woes to talk about the dropping standards of living and the increase in corruption. Lacking in accurate census data, Nigeria is estimated to have a population of 217 million, 70% of these being youths. In this estimate, 42% are under the age of 15 (Worldometer, 2023). Another survey puts the age bracket of these large percentage of youths in Nigeria at 18-29 years, making Nigeria the youngest country in Africa (Akinyemi and Jacob, 2022). With the median age of Nigerians at 18.1 years, Nigeria indeed has a teeming population of young people.

The situation on ground in Ibadan, its environs and the whole of Oyo State in Nigeria, is a generation of young people in a precarious condition. Large numbers of school leavers who are not suitable for tertiary education, occasioned by lowered standards of

education and the institutionalization of examination malpractices at both the primary and secondary schools.

Increase in crime rates among the young, especially as it pertains to criminal acquisition of wealth is the order of the day. This phenomenon plays out among the males in efforts at swindling, robberies, cybercrimes, kidnappings and ritual killings for money, among others. Among young females, the loose life has become popular for acquiring material gains. Of course, we have a fair portion of young persons who are enterprising and taking laudable strides in the right direction, but the vast majority fall under the previous description.

The decrease in levels and standards of living due to the economic woes of the nation seems to have compounded the dilemma of the young. Everyone seems to want to make money by the fastest possible ways and with the least efforts. Yet, no nation has ever developed on falsehood and crime (Proverbs 14:34). This paper addresses what it takes for the next generation of adult Nigerians to have the essential ingredient for holistic national development and visionary leadership.

2. Integrity – A Core Value for Development

Integrity simply defined is the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles. To describe integrity as it plays out in lives of persons, institutions or communities, it encapsulates these qualities – rectitude, honourableness, good character, principles, ethics, morality, virtue, trustworthiness among others (Mirriam-Webster Dictionary, 2023). Derived from the Latin word *integritas*, integrity connotes wholesomeness and the state of being undivided, indicating that a person of integrity is the same within and without. He can be relied upon, does what he says he will do and acts ethically correct no matter the pressures.

A people of integrity will by the definition proffered above, have value for what is true, will abhor and refuse to honour untruthfulness and ill-gotten wealth. They will value hard work and diligence as channels for successful enterprise. Top among their expectation from those who lead them will be integrity of character and credibility (Kouzes and Posner, 2011).

Where integrity is embedded as a societal value, parents and guardians will teach and model these traits; leaders will lead with integrity and policies of government will make it difficult for deviants to have a field day. Transparency in governance and in financial dealings have been the standard for development in many countries. In his paper, “Integrity – Foundation of Good Government”, Dr Emsley D Tromp, the president of the Bank of the Netherlands, proffered conditions necessary for economic efficiency and the eradication of corruption, which their country had practiced earlier on (Tromp, 2010). Among these are:

- Transparent government financial operations.

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- Strong management of public resources and establishment of stable regulatory environment.
 - Transparent budgetary procedures.
 - More effective and accountable economic and financial institutions.

The bottom line in Emsley Tromp's submission is that accountability and transparency of government institutions and officials have helped the Netherlands in its journey in developing as a nation. Integrity helped Netherlands and is still helping her development.

Countries we applaud as developed today all had their times in history when they were in chaos, and had to decide that doing the right things and doing them the right way, was the way to go. Great Britain's history is fraught with periods when the people needed to have paradigm shifts to allow ethics and truth to rule their nation. It took British slavery abolitionists over 50 years (1770s - 1834) of struggle with the government and parliament of their days before they finally succeeded in effecting the Act (Henry, 2023). At the height of the British Industrial Revolution, when children were used in factories for long hours in harzardous conditions, for a few to get rich, right thinking British people pushed for the enactment of the Factory Act (1833), and the Mines Act (1842) (The British Library, 2023). Today they have a nation that works, where Nigerians have targeted for migration. Fruits of integrity in personal lives and families include wholesome behaviour, good mental health, committed workforce, forward looking and credible leaders at local, state and national levels.

Adelaja posits in his paper, "How to transform a nation through truth and honesty", that there is a strong relationship between truth, honesty and national development and that any country that we see progressing and forward looking, is fundamentally based on the principles of integrity (Adelaja, 2022). He further opined that national transformation will continue to be a mirage in Nigeria as long as the citizens are as corrupt as the politicians from whom they collect largesse in exchange for votes.

As long the ordinary citizens pay bribes to corrupt officials, to help them get waivers from doing the right things, in the right ways and at the right times, it means lack of integrity has become systemic. Albert Einstein rightly said, "Whoever is careless with the truth in small matters, cannot be trusted with important matters" (Adelaja, 2022). Such is the Nigerian situation because, it is the citizenry that produce their leaders; hence the nation's progress remains hampered because of the systemic lack of integrity. The undoing of the land presently is that those who should model integrity, as elders and leaders have only the opposite character to present as models for the teens and youths. "Currently, we live in society that celebrates the rich without questioning what people did to acquire wealth, and this scenario has slowly but surely defined a new normal for the younger generation who aim to be rich by any means possible" Chukwuka, 2021).

As it is obvious that lack of integrity is the root cause of corruption and its resultant effects on Nigeria's development, it is of utmost necessity that we pursue its return into our societal culture.

3. Evidence of Lack of Integrity in Ibadan Society

The society in question in this paper covers Ibadan city and its environs. Ibadan, the capital of Oyo State comprises eleven Local Government Areas (LGAs); five of these are Urban (Ibadan North, North East, North West, South East and South West), while six of them are suburban (Egbeda, Lagelu, Ona-Ara, Akinyele, Oluyole and Iddo). The estimated population of Ibadan is 3.6 million in the metropolis and about 6 million with the suburbs combined (Oyo State Nigeria -Population Statistics, 2021).

The population is made up of people of all age groups. Even though the target population in this paper are the young within the suburban LGAs mostly, it takes the older to teach or impact the younger. Since no one can give to another what he does not have, the older people are also targeted, so that they can be instruments of the desired change for a better Nigeria in the near future.

3.1. Personal Lives

Integrity says, you are who you are when you think that no one is watching. Your true character is that which you really are on the inside, irrespective of what you portray when eyes are on you. A person of integrity maintains that quality all the time, irrespective of the pressures around.

The paramount evidence of lack of integrity starts with the individuals. Society is full of

- Persons who cheat others in the market place, either by exorbitant pricing or direct shortchanging of customers.
- Persons who tell lies to escape doing what is right; give false evidence on oath in the law courts; alter prices on receipts to defraud institutions; are involved in bribery and similar evils.
- Individuals who commit atrocities as rape, murders, kidnaps, ritual killings to get rich, among others.

These are evidenced in the news every day in the target areas and the whole nation at large.

3.2. Family Life

The individuals living with the core values of lack of integrity cannot produce families that are different. Moses when instructing the nation of Israel before they entered the land of Cannan, asked the parents and guardians to first put the law of God for righteous living in their own hearts. He said that was when they would be able to teach it accurately to the younger generations. (Deuteronomy 6:4-9)

Evidence of lack of integrity abound at the family levels.

- Parents who ask their children to lie when creditors are around, abound. By these and similar acts, family heads entrench lack of truthfulness as family norms.
- What do you think happens to a child whose parent/guardian pays depraved school teachers to “help” his ward pass examinations? This parent has demonstrated to him that he does not need to follow due process to succeed in life. The foundation for fraud, bribery and corruption is well laid within the family. When under pressure for funds that child would commit crimes as serious as kidnapping or ritual killing to get those funds. These and worse occurrences are the order of the day.
- Within many families, different forms of assault are perpetrated from fathers on mothers and the children. Verbal, physical, even sexual abuse is on the increase. The children of these homes have simply been taught to be violent and cover up when interrogated.

As the family is the bedrock of any society, it is obvious why the evidences of lack of integrity abound everywhere.

3.3. Society

As a result of lack of personal/family integrity, the communities are dysfunctional. The parents have eaten sour grapes, but it is the children whose teeth are on edge (Ezekiel 18:2). The prevailing situation in many of the communities covered within Ibadan is that of an increase in vices which include but are not limited to these:

- Unstable families where fathers are either absent or uncommitted to providing for the children.
- Young mothers (often times teenagers) who have not completed secondary education, impregnated by young men who have no stable jobs or skills to provide for themselves and their families.
- Many disillusioned youths without prospects for a better future hooked on drugs and alcohol, setting the stage for many mental health casualties.
- Robberies, gangsterism/cultism, internet fraud and selling off lands previously sold, and similar crimes.
- Those who suddenly become affluent are admired without questioning how that happened in the absence any tangible enterprise linked to them.
- In rural and suburban communities, the youths have abandoned the farms and shun career in Agriculture, preferring to be commercial motorcycle riders, and to do similar daily paid jobs.
- Due to ignorance of what is right in the society, many in the communities have already begun to view cybercrimes among youths as a skill to be acquired thereby despising enterprise, perseverance and diligent efforts.

- In response to peer pressure and the 'need' to be acclaimed as 'rich', the youths captured in the situations above, resort to all kinds of vices that are offshoots of thought patterns void of integrity.

When this generation of young people become the elders, will they have better values to teach their children than what they themselves are? As it stands, the above is the present pattern of life evolving in this society.

Where did things go wrong?

Where should right values begin to be put in place?

4. How Can Culture Change or Be Transformed

Culture simply defined is the totality of the way of life of a people. Culture comprises the learned patterns of behaviour of a people and their underlining assumptions. The patterns of behaviour are what we see, which include their dress patterns, their food, their artifacts, ceremonies/rights of passage and how they generally behave. For every behaviour seen on the outside, underlining assumptions are influencing such behaviours (Kwast, 2009). As Kwast explains that underneath what we observe as people's visible cultural patterns, lies layers of factors that influence what people do.

BEHAVIOUR: These are the customs, products, and language. This comprises what people do or what they consider as appropriate behaviour.

VALUES: These are standards of conduct and determinants of judging what ought to be done, what is good or best. Values answers for people, the question, 'What is normal in order to conform to the pattern of life of that community'? So, we see that values people hold influence their behaviours.

Figure 1

BELIEFS: Here, what the true belief of people is, determines their values. Theoretical beliefs do not influence values; rather it is what they believe in their hearts that determine what they value.

WORLDVIEW is at the core of every culture. It is the lens as it were, with which the people see things and interpret reality. Worldview assumptions may not have been proven and may be myths, but they are accepted as reality. They directly influence the beliefs and values, which ultimately define the behaviour of the people.

If any aspect of culture is going to change, it must begin at the worldview level, and work its way to their patterns of behaviour. Worldview is so powerful that it still controls people even after they receive a new belief system. As long as their worldview is not changed, they still behave as they did before they received their new beliefs (Kraft, 2009). This phenomenon explains the syncretic behaviours of some variants of Christianity.

The core of any culture is often guarded by elders whose duty it is, to impart such to the younger generations. We have observed that integrity has become a lost aspect of Nigeria's culture, and is now a needed ingredient for national development, societal health and prosperity. We therefore need to explore ways to restore this virtue back into our national worldview. But, how does culture change? Using the onion analogy, the core (centre) of the onion is the only part that can reproduce an onion. The outer layers of the onion are not reproducible. If we keep trying to change behaviours, values and beliefs without addressing the people's worldview, there cannot be any enduring result. People will still manifest their old patterns of values and behaviour.

5. Areas Where Integrity Must Be Inculcated in the Society and Nation

1. Individuals should come to the realization that they need to be persons with their own personal integrity. When people have been taught to have a sense of worth over their own persons, they begin to see it is demeaning for them to be liars, cheats or to have bad reputation before others.
2. Families should pride themselves based on the integrity of their members, the truthfulness and transparency of their children's sources of wealth, and sharply oppose sudden wealth that cannot be accounted for. Traditional cultural values that frown on promiscuity and loose life of ladies should be upheld. The home and the parents in the home should decide on what they wish to be known by, and teach such to their children and wards.
3. Community and political leadership should be above board. People with integrity should be those who become our leaders.
4. Government and its officials should be credible. Without integrity at this level, there cannot be national orientation that will successfully eradicate corruption.

6. Who Does What?

All hands will have to be on deck to tackle a systemic lack of truth, honesty and uprightness. When a good seed is sown in the soil, you expect to be able to re-propagate it and still get that seed with all its original features.

Stakeholders for the return of the vital ingredient of Integrity will have to include:

- The teachers of Religion who will teach the fear of God to the people. This cannot be achieved by those who practice or teach religion as a duty. Only the passionate can persevere in efforts to change the warped worldview assumptions of the young Nigerians of today.
- The community and opinion leaders who are not part of the 'bandwagon' of corrupt elders will need to arise to speak for and live out the values that will give birth to the return of integrity in their domains.
- Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) will need to come up with innovative ways to teach Integrity to government and call government officials to become accountable to the society. Example of an area that can be very fruitful is the schools system, where NGOs can mount up pressure and insist that all teachers who 'help' pupils writing the common entrance examinations, or students sitting for their secondary school certificate examinations, should be permanently sent out of the teaching profession. Since we have enrollment of pupils and students in very high percentage in schools (public and private) in Ibadan, next to the home, the school system should be targeted.
- Government parastatals and ministries saddled with various responsibilities are in very good position to effect a new orientation. These would be able to present a covering for all other efforts by nongovernmental agencies, if they work in synergy.

What To Do

The curriculum for this proposed worldview change is not far-fetched. On paper, Nigeria has a National Orientation Policy (National Orientation Agency, 2021). Strategic Plan for 2021-2026. We do not need to reinvent the wheel. In this plan, the goal for Strategic Pillar 3 is, to "Positively change attitudes, values and behaviours that promote peace, harmony and national development". Its priority areas are

- a. Citizen engagement
- b. Public enlightenment
- c. Civic responsibility

The plans if followed, should have turned Nigerian youth into people of great integrity and great hope for the nation's development. Of relevance to the discourse in this paper is the fact the plans include hopes that the nation will be rid of corruption. What laudable plans! The problem this paper sees and presents for solution, is that those who will make

an impact with their teachings, should first be people who practice what they teach. The leadership has to show that they mean what they say. Worldview changes precede changes in values and behaviours, hence the need for parents, guardians, teachers, community leaders and elders to be first, people who teach by life before teaching by precepts.

Conclusions

In exploring avenues for inculcating the value of integrity into young Nigerians, particularly in Ibadan and its environs, this paper concludes that

1. The status quo must change. It is unacceptable for the young people on whom the future of our country lies, to be allowed to continue living lives that lack integrity and truth when we know that it does not augur well for future progress and prosperity for the nation.
2. Since the lack of integrity has been deeply embedded in the present culture of both the elderly and the young, it will require a deep level culture change aimed at bringing about a worldview that agrees that integrity, uprightness should be the norm.
3. To achieve this feat, everyone is a stakeholder. The individuals in families, the families in the communities, the leaders and elders in communities, the teachers both secular and religious, government and non-governmental agencies.
4. The fear of God should be taught from the home front and the religious groups should take up the challenge to be the change agents of these times.

Recommendations

Concerned persons and groups who have the understanding that things are wrong, should arise to put in their own part in the inculcating integrity into young persons in Ibadan Area and nationally. This paper recommends that there be a proliferation of efforts in these areas:

1. Orientation for parents and guardians based on written ethics, code of conduct and responsible parenting. Aspects of the National Orientation policy programme book could be adapted.
2. Organize and run intentional neighbourhood clubs for children and teens. These could be sports based, faith based, or intellect based. Here the activities should include Story-telling sessions where integrity, uprightness, diligence and the likes are portrayed and taught.
3. School teachers' re-orientation to return to ethics of the profession. The ministry of education and the Teachers' Commission should spearhead this aspect. Non-governmental agencies should help to spur these government agencies, and hold them accountable to enforce teachers' compliance to ethics.

4. Use of all media avenues (regular and social) to air jingles and playlets that resonate with integrity as key for personal, community and national progress.
5. NGOs and Faith bodies to coin appropriate ways to amplify the government's national orientation agency plans for the young in Nigeria.
6. Funding by government and philanthropic organizations should be made available to societies and groups who are committed to doing any of the recommendations above.

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